

The Effectiveness Of Arbitration In Settling Islamic Banking Disputes

Ahmed Moustafa AL-Dabousi El-Sayed

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Abstract

This scientific paper discusses one of the types of banking disputes, which is banking disputes of an Islamic nature that are among the most complex, important and difficult disputes. And that is due to reasons, which includes the difference in the legal source that governs the banking operations carried out by Islamic banking institutions, and its relevance to the technical and substantive aspects of banking operations.

Thus, it may be difficult for the judiciary to settle them, and the issue of settling these disputes has become a matter that disturbs those dealing in this field, given the obstacles and problems that may accompany the judiciary that are not in line with the advanced and renewed nature of Islamic banking operations, paving the way for arbitration to come as a mean to settling these disputes.

The research reached several recommendations; the most important of which is the necessity to codifying the provisions of Islamic laws related to Islamic banking and financial operations and their new institutions, and their respective tools and contracts, by placing them in the form of legal articles that facilitate the adjudication of related lawsuits in order to achieve the renewed legitimate interest and meet the changing needs of institutions and individuals, as well as the need to establish a special center or entity to settle Islamic banking disputes.

Introduction

Islamic banking disputes are among the most complex, important and difficult disputes confronting the commercial field in the Middle East, and that is due to several reasons, which include the differentiation in the legal sources that governs the banking operations carried out by Islamic banking institutions; as Islamic financial banking transactions are distinguished by the necessity of their compatibility with the provisions of Islamic Sharia, which requires banks and customers to adhere to the provisions of Sharia law and not to violate its doctrines, and simultaneously obliges the judge to be familiar with the Sharia provisions of Islamic banking, and its various transactions, in order to determine the extent of their safety and compatibility with the provisions of Islamic Sharia.

Moreover, given its attachment to the technical and substantive aspects of banking operations; it may be difficult for the judiciary to settle these Islamic banking disputes, causing them become a matter that weary those dealing in this field, due to the obstacles that may accompany the judiciary who may not be compatible with the advanced and renewed nature of Islamic banking operations. These issues are due to the weakness of the Islamic culture and Islamic banking experiences of the judges, which usually results in prolonging litigation in disputes arising from Islamic banking operations, of which, time is a major and important factor.

Looking at the usage of arbitration as a mean of settling Islamic banking disputes, we find that despite the attempts of many countries and organizations specialized in the field of arbitration to utilize it as a means to settle those Islamic banking disputes, we find a great reluctance on the part of Islamic banking institutions to resort to arbitration to settle their banking disputes. We find this reluctance evident through not including the arbitration clause in these institutions' dealings with their respective clients, or with their counterparts of other banking institutions, as these bodies tend to litigate before the courts, and would bluntly justify this by the existence of universally accepted norms and rules, which have been repeatedly applying stable judicial rulings in most parts of the world, as though as it was a unified global law, which makes it easier for the banking institution to resort to the judiciary while it is certain that it would safeguard its rights.

The main constraint of using arbitration as a means to settle banking disputes lies in the loss of trust of the parties in the field of Islamic banking operations in the arbitration system as a means to settle disputes, and resorting to the judiciary system to settle these differences, as it is one of the best means of resolving those disputes from their point of view, despite the length of litigation procedures before the judiciary, and the lack of the necessary banking experience for judges in the field of Islamic banking transactions, which would always lead the dispute to an unfair settlement.

Another issue is that, the operations carried out by Islamic banking institutions differ from those carried out by other regular banking organizations. As the Islamic financial banking transactions are distinguished by the

necessity to comply with the provisions of Islamic Sharia law, and this matter requires banks and customers to adhere to the provisions of Sharia law and not violate it, which is not actually applied in “regular” banking institutions, necessitating that the judges to be familiar with the all Sharia provisions of Islamic banking transactions, in order to be safely satisfied with its compatibility with the provisions of Islamic law.

1-Technical difficulties facing the judiciary in settling Islamic banking disputes

Disputes between Islamic banking institutions and their clients are not necessarily of a legal nature, as the cause of the difference is often about technicalities, or in the implementation of the Islamic banking processes of the institution which clients have reasons to dispute, and which is often difficult for court judges to decide on. Thus, judges often assign specialized technical experts to provide them with an opinion on these issues.

Examples of these technical matters that raise difficulties in settling Islamic banking disputes before the courts, include the lack of clarity of Islamic banking transactions for judges, and the lacking hereof of the codification of the provisions of Islamic Sharia, that which is related to Islamic banking and financial transactions, their respective institutions, tools and new contracts, by placing them in the form of legal articles that would facilitate for the judge's ruling on the lawsuits presented to achieve the renewed legitimate interest, and meet the changing needs of institutions and individuals.

On the same note, the UAE legislator has recently allowed the establishment of Islamic banks, or Islamic branches in banks, and in this way, it differs from traditional banks. The main difference between them is that Islamic banks perform the function of financial intermediation without isolating the risks, as a conventional bank does. Therefore, the clients who deposited their money in Islamic banks on the basis of “mudarabah” bears the risk of the end user of the funds. Thus, the role of the bank is to “conduct the business” (in the language of speculation) or “managing the account” (in the language of modern banks), for which, the bank receives fees in exchange for its management.

Hence, the modern Islamic bank in reality has adopted the modern trend that banks have taken, which is to provide the opportunity for savers to take risks directly. Whereas the traditional -None Islamic- banks are nothing more than a financial intermediary that trades in debts, with the aim of making a profit through the difference between the interest rates; as it keeps customers' deposits against a low interest, and provides them to other clients in the form of high interest loans or financial credits, in addition to the regular services of money transfer, checks, currencies, etc.

However, despite the establishment of these Islamic banks and Islamic branches, by researching the UAE Federal Law No. 6 Of 1985 AD regarding banks, financial institutions and Islamic investment companies, we find that it does not contain general legal rules governing contracts for operations and Islamic banking and investment services, which is a legislative deficiency that must be mitigated, especially since some local Islamic banks and companies have tended to diversify the methods and forms of Islamic banking, such as the sale of murabahah to the one who is ordered to buy, speculation, and the sale of tawarruq, reversed tawarruq, sale of salam, to name a few, and these transactions are accomplished by means of complex and overlapping agreements that constitute a system of contracts that must be viewed as a single package and not as is the case now, where these conventions are divided and viewed independently when the judicial claim are commenced, and then the judge must be aware in the first place with all the intersecting legal provisions for the transactions presented to him.

Accordingly, the modernity in Islamic banking transactions increases the legal risks in the Islamic banking business, as there are not many judicial precedents in this type of disputes, which the judge can rely on, and one of these precedents is a case decided by British courts such as: Islamic Investment Company of the Gulf Vs. Symphony Gems. Whereby, the investment company entered into a financing transaction with the defendant (Symphony), which ended in a dispute that was submitted to the British courts, based on a prior agreement between the two parties, which requires resorting to the British judiciary in the event of a dispute, and this example, although it is indirect for the case we are looking at here, it gives an accurate picture of what is happening in the relevant legal framework, and the reason is that (Symphony) did not pay any of the installments entailed by it, and to understand the legal formula of the murabaha contract, the court summoned two experts to explain this, and one of them concluded - after considering the nature and conditions of the contract - that the agreement in question does not have the basic characteristics of a murabahah contract.

However, based on the text of the agreement, and abiding by British law, in concluding the contract, which was the foundation of the agreement, and therefore is binding on its parties, the court ruled in favor of the plaintiff, which is the Islamic Investment Company of the Gulf.

We notice here, when examining this issue in detail, two things, the first is the injudiciousness of some contracts conducted by some Islamic institutions, as they seek refuge in the civil judiciary to reap profits through it which is a major problem that needs serious pause from concerned parties, jurists and researchers, to find a remedy for. And the second, is the danger of deciding on issues of Islamic transactions through civil judiciary, which results in the occurrence of injustice on one of the parties involved or the other.

Also, among these precedents is the case which the Malaysian judiciary decided on, the substance of the case was the conclusion of a contract in the form of a forward sale price between the bank (the plaintiff) and the defendant, according to which a real estate and a group of assets would be purchased. It is worth noting here that the plaintiff was not the only financier of the process, but rather one of the financiers and, at the request of the defendant, had organized the full financing of the project through several financial institutions, as it had played the role of the financier and agent for the defendant, except that after the completion of the process, the client – defendant- failed to pay the installments.

Moreover, there was a condition in the contract stating that if the customer fails to pay, the rest of the installments are to be expedited, and without having to wait for their time to come, and the customer must fulfill them, and despite the customer's request to restructure the concluded contract and the bank's approval of that, the customer failed again to provide the bank with the agreed upon installments again, and failed to declare some specific information requested by the bank; Therefore, the bank was forced to file the case to the civil court to collect its dues.

After the litigation procedures were completed, which lasted for nearly ten years, the court ruled in favor of the plaintiff (the bank) that the defendant pay the installments due, in addition to compensation for the damages incurred by the bank as a result of non-payment. Additionally, it is worth noting here that the client tried to question the validity of the contract from the Sharia point of view, which was rejected by the court indicating that this is a way to evade payment, and that the problem is in the interpretation of the contract and not in its legality.

Another case worth noting here, is the It is also one of the judicial precedents in settling Islamic banking disputes, a dispute brought before the Tunis preliminary court, whereby a company entered into a murabaha contract with a bank to buy goods, and after completing the process and charging the company's liability with a debt for the benefit of the bank, the company refused the fulfillment of the contract, citing the invalidity of the murabahah contract due to its violation of banking laws and its lacking hereof of the essential pillars according to Islamic jurisprudence, filing a case with the preliminary Court of Tunis requesting the appointment of an expert in accounts to review the application of the terms of the contract, then went beyond this request to argue for the nullity of the murabahah contract, whereby and the court decided to reject the case.

From all the above, we deduct that the non-specialization of the ordinary judiciary in adjudicating disputes arising from Islamic banking transactions are attributed to the following:

- A. The operating rules of Islamic banks or the Islamic branches of traditional banks differs from that of traditional businesses and banks rules. Whereas most of the rules for working in traditional banks are derived from legislations and regulations far from the reality of the Islamic community, the rules of Islamic banks are based, for example in the field of financing, on the basis of private contracts and agreements without actually having legal support, complementary rules, or similar tax benefits to traditional banks. Therefore, we find Islamic banks suffers from taxes that are taken on the profits that are distributed on investment deposits, as they are not treated on the basis that they are part of the banking total costs. In conventional banks, on the other hand, the interest paid by them is part of their total costs, which constitutes more pressure on Islamic banks. In the same context, the Cairo Economic Court made a ruling* in connection with one of the Islamic banking operations, that the murabahah and its contracts, specifically, the claim voucher, have failed to specify the percentage of the delay compensation, and that whenever these contracts are devoid of the agreement interest determination, then the legal interest determined in accordance with the provisions of Article (226) of the civil regulation is to be used, and this was the matter with which the court decides to obligate the defendant to pay 5% annually, as simple interest for the delay compensation.
- B. The lack of sufficient experience among judges to settle disputes arising from Islamic banking transactions, as these transactions relates to extremely complex financial and legal issues, thus it needs academic and technical qualifications that must be a part of the judges competencies, but the reality is that these qualifications are not available in most judges, due to the fact that most of these judges were graduates of law schools that does not teach subjects related to Islamic financing, in addition to the relatively new emergence of Islamic banking. To illustrate this point, Islamic banks have put in place a system for the documentary credit process in line with the provisions of Islamic Sharia, called "Murabaha Documentary Credits Financing" which is a completely novel and different credit system from that used in traditional banking, so the Islamic bank through this mechanism opens the documentary credit in the name of the bank and in its favor, with the aim of realizing its ownership of the goods. Then, after the arrival of the documents for shipping the goods, the bank sells them to the customer for a deferred price to be paid in installments agreed upon between the Islamic bank and the customer. Thus, if an Islamic bank finances the approval of a deal to import cars into Egypt for example, all documents of this deal will be stating in the name of the Islamic bank as the beneficiary,

and that is what will be shown the customer in accordance with the Islamic banks' business rules. Accordingly, if, after receiving the cars, the customer refuses to pay the debt, and the Islamic bank resorted to the judiciary to request the cancellation of the precautionary seizure on the client's money, then the judge will reject that on the grounds that the cars had in fact arrived in Egypt under the name of the Islamic bank, according to the documents provided to the customer by the bank's endorsement, so the importer was not the customer, and the credit line was not opened under the client's name, and there is no escape for the Islamic bank from having to explain this type of Islamic financing in the trade to the judge, which will continue for a period of time, at which the customer can very well sell cars in any country before the seizure is placed on them, which may lead to the loss of the bank's rights, which is the direct result of the lacking of clarity in Islamic financing in trade for the majority of judges and their inability to comprehend these transactions. Likewise, another example that clearly indicates the lacking of clarity of Islamic banking operations for judges, when one of the Gulf Islamic banks tried to securitize the debt granted to a Syrian citizen, so the case was presented to the judge in two ways: The first method: the link between the original debt before it was securitized, and the debt after it was securitized, without stating or clarifying the reason securitization in the Islamic bank, the second method: not linking the amount outstanding, thus doubling the amount of the debt, as the Islamic bank can very well claim the debt and the bonds issued with it.

- C. All Islamic banks have Sharia bodies that monitor the extent to which the operations they offer are compatible with the provisions of Islamic Sharia laws, and the source of legislation for any Islamic institution is in its own Sharia body. Therefore, the judge must, in the first place, be familiar with the Sharia provisions of the transactions presented to him, which is most difficult as most judges are not qualified in this important aspect, thus untenable to be fully aware of the issues of the Islamic banking industry. As an example of this, the sale of organized tawarruq in its two types, both banking and reverse, despite the agreement of the three Fiqh Councils, namely the Islamic Fiqh Council of the Islamic World League in Makkah Al-Mukarramah, the International Islamic Fiqh Academy in Jeddah, and the European Council for Fatwa and Research, and many seminars and jurisprudential and economic conferences, on the prohibition of organized tawarruq, and although these colleges include in their membership those who are originally members of the Sharia boards in banks, some Islamic banks in the this country – UAE- still apply all kinds of tawarruq treatment without being bound by the controls or standards stipulated by the jurists in order for this transaction to be validated in accordance with the overall rules of Islamic law, which makes the matter of verifying the compliance of these transactions with the provisions of Islamic law burdened by and under the ruling of the judge.

In the event of a dispute between the bank and its client, especially in light of the failure to activate the text of Article (5) of the Islamic Banking, Institutions and Companies Law, which states: “*By a decision of the Council of Ministers, a supreme Sharia body is formed, comprising legal, legal and banking elements, and shall assume supreme supervision over banks. Islamic financial institutions and investment companies, to verify the legality of their transactions, in accordance with the provisions of Islamic law, as well as express opinion on matters presented to these bodies during the exercise of their activities, and the opinion of the supreme body shall be binding on the aforementioned bodies, and this body shall be attached to the Ministry of Islamic Affairs and Endowments*”. As the existence of this body and its being independent will provide a guarantee for clients and would greatly assist the judge in determining the Sharia ruling on the issue as it is a neutral party.

It is clear from the foregoing that the inability of the judiciary to settle disputes in which one of the parties is an Islamic bank is due first to the weakness in the protection provided by legislation and laws for Islamic banking transactions, and secondly due to the lack of clarity of Islamic banking operations for judges and their inability to interpret them, due to the lacking of background information pertinent to the field in question.

2-Feasibility of resorting to arbitration in Islamic banking disputes

New banking and financial services have entered the Islamic financial stage, almost equal to or more than the banking services recognized by banking institutions, and among the most important of these operations are Interest rate swaps, currency swaps, speculative operations on foreign currencies, and securitization operations, all of which were not legislated, organized nor established with clear rules like traditional banking operations.

Dealing in these banking operations is largely based on the element of time, thus speed becomes a guarantee of success in concluding the deal, or achieving the desired profit, and the work is characterized by subtle specialization, and technical characteristics that develops on a daily bases.

Subsequently, resorting to the judiciary to settle disputes arising from these banking operations, especially Islamic ones, becomes inconsistent with its nature. It has become certain that resorting to the judicial means to resolve banking disputes in general does not comply with the requirements of the times and the need for international transactions. Indeed, the vary absence of international courts specialized in examining these disputes, states that it is an important and acceptable explanation for the growing role of arbitration in the field of international banking disputes.

Therefore, it was imperative to find suitable means that would help settle disputes arising in these Islamic banking operations, which are characterized by specialized technical characteristics to a large extent, in a balanced or acceptable manner that fulfills the interests of Islamic banking institutions and does not threaten the interests of clients, and arbitration was one of the most important of these means because of its advantages. As there are many reasons that may push the litigants in the Islamic banking field to resort to arbitration, where by, those in charge of cross-border banking, trade and investment transactions have realized that the state's judiciary is overburdened with cases and is painfully shackled by procedural restrictions that make it slow in its performance, costly in its expenses, and inadequate in its solutions, which does not commensurate with the Islamic banking operations, that by its nature requires a certain discord, a kind of secrecy and speed. Therefore, dealers may appreciate, in these processes that resorting to arbitration may provide them with better justice than that provided by state courts. Arbitration is a private judiciary established by the parties with their agreement, and they choose its members, and entrust it to settle their disputes in a manner that does not fuel discord between them and preserves the continuity of the relationship and dealings.

Moreover, arbitration provides the parties involved in Islamic banking disputes better conditions under which they can reach the desired result, by submitting their cases to arbitrators with technical and legal expertise that are not usually acquired by judges working in state courts. This would facilitate the speedy resolution to the Islamic banking disputes in a more rapid way, at lower costs, with less complicated procedures, and in a way that preserves the confidentiality of their banking information.

3-1 Feasibility of resorting to arbitration in Islamic banking disputes

Flexibility of arbitration procedures:

The speed and economy in the procedures are among the best features of the arbitration system, making it the most preferable means to traders and businessmen to resolve disputes. Arbitration is a judiciary that is free from the systems of judicial procedures that are initiated by the courts, does not adhere to specific trial procedures, neither legal nor statutory, and the parties to the dispute are the ones who control the time period for consideration of the subject of the arbitration, and the arbitration panel, and according to the parties' desire, may take the necessary measures to expedite the settlement of the case before it.

Additionally, it is worth noting that the arbitration panel examines documents in their original language, without the need for a translation that would otherwise take more time, effort and expense, without obliging the parties to submit the original documents, but rather is usually satisfied with the image, which is completely compatible with electronic banking. It is moreover worth noting that the flexibility in arbitration procedures is what would incline the parties to resort to it, as they would do without the many rules and procedures that govern the judiciary, thus some laws have been keen to give the right to litigants in arbitration disputes to hold their sessions in any country whose legislation may contribute to increasing the speed of arbitration dispute settlement in addition to trying to establish more simplified and expedited procedures to obtain the order of execution, to settle the dispute and end it as soon as possible, and it necessary seems, that the advantage of arbitration is in its speed, and prompt justice.

The nature of Islamic banking operations may, in most cases, require direct and rapid implementation, due to the sudden change in currency and interest rates. Organized murabahah operations, in both traditional banking and Islamic types, for example, are affected by the sudden change in prices (such as currency exchange rates, interest), or due to a non-compliance with conditions, or bank accreditation, which may lead to direct damages to the Islamic banking institution, or to its customers. Therefore, it is necessary to resolve any dispute that occurs in connection with these operations as soon as possible, so that the postponement does not lead to larger differences that may directly harm the banking institution,

or one of its customers. Finally, it is worth noting that the rules governing arbitration attempted to achieve this advantage by specifying a specific period for the formation of the arbitration panel, and a specific period for issuing the arbitration ruling.

International enforcement of arbitral rulings:

Arbitration rulings are characterized by a much wider scope in terms of implementation at the international level, compared to judgments issued by judicial courts, whereas judgments issued by judicial courts are not often executed outside the country in which the judgment was issued in a direct manner, parties prefer to resort directly to arbitration, as it is easily implementable for the arbitration rulings issued abroad. To that end, the desired goal of the parties resorting to arbitration as a means of settling disputes among themselves, as the Cairo Regional Center for International Commercial Arbitration went in a ruling to enable the party for whom the judgment is issued to obtain their right through the easiest procedures and without incurring the hassle and hardship of resorting to the state's judiciary, and the waste of time, effort and expenses that this entails.

Additionally, the New York Convention of 1958 issued on the recognition and implementation of foreign arbitrators' judgments provided a facilitated procedural system for the implementation of foreign arbitration rulings in an attempt to remove obstacles to the implementation of arbitrators' judgments outside the countries in which they were issued, or that applied their law to the dispute or arbitration procedures, as well as the first paragraph of Article 54 of the Washington DC Convention of 1965, stipulating that each contracting state recognizes the judgment issued based on the provisions of this agreement and guarantees the implementation of the financial obligations imposed by the judgment, as if it was finally issued by a local court, and this agreement has created the International Center for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID).

Thus, the parties - the banking institution and its clients - will avoid the difficulties of implementing a court ruling in a country other than the one in which it was issued; by resorting to arbitration at this center whose judgment can be executed in a country other than the country of its issuance, without any difficulty, thus, in the context of encouraging the implementation of arbitration judgments, court rulings tend to grant the judge the discretionary power to grant or refuse recognition of arbitration rulings, even if reasons for refusal are available, including those related to public order, this was done to confront those who may be undertaken by some courts, those who attempt to put obstacles in place to limit the effectiveness of the provisions of the agreements for the implementation of arbitration provisions, such as if the competent court refuses to issue the order for execution, given that the judgment violates the interest rate specified in the law and related to public order.

The judiciary relies in this on the phrase used in paragraph (2) of Article 5 of the 1958 New York Convention Concerning the Recognition and Execution of Foreign Arbitrators' Judgments, which states that *"The competent authority in the country requested to recognize and implement the arbitrators' judgment may refuse recognition and enforcement if it becomes evident to it: (a) that the law of that country does not allow the dispute to be settled through arbitration, (b) that recognition or implementation of the arbitrators' ruling is in contravention of public order in this paragraph used the phrase "it is permissible" to refuse, and the phrase "must" is not used, which expresses in the opinion of the American judiciary the discretionary power enjoyed by the judge, even in light of the availability of reasons for rejection, including those related to the system of the public order"*.

Moreover, the American judiciary recognized the arbitration ruling issued in one of the disputes, on the basis that the facts of the public order violation are based on the claim of non-compliance with the rules governing the arbitration, which was not quickly objected to the violation of the opposing party despite the possibility of reforming the violation, and this was considered a waiver of the objection, if it is possible to object at the specified time, and the objection had not been completed, then raising it at the stage of implementation or nullity is late and courts tend to reject it within the framework of their discretionary authority, despite the availability of reason for refusing the implementation and recognition of the arbitration ruling.

The finality of the ruling of arbitration:

The finality of the arbitration ruling is one of the most important advantages of using this mean in settling Islamic banking disputes, as it enables the party in whose favor it is judged to obtain its rights

without obstacles created by the party against whom it is ruled, which is exactly what happens before the courts during the settlement of Islamic banking disputes. Moreover, it will be possible for the parties to stipulate a condition on the arbitration agreement that prevents the possibility of appealing against the arbitrators' rulings issued.

Further, in the absence of this text in an arbitration law in the country the arbitration is carried on, such as the text of Article (52) of the Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, which states that *“Arbitration judgments issued in accordance with the provisions of this law shall not be challenged by any of the methods of appeal stipulated In the Civil and Commercial Procedure Law”*, in addition to article (23) of the Regulations for the Mediation and Arbitration Center System of the Union of Arab Banks stipulated that *“The two parties, as a result of submitting their dispute to arbitration in accordance with this system, are bound to implement the content of the ruling issued without any delay, and the judgment issued is considered final, and is not subject to any method of review or appeal”*. Considering the arbitrators' judgment as final and not subject to review in any way of judicial review would thus enhance the confidence of the disputing parties, and their certainty of the veracity of the judgment, instead of allowing the room to re-present the dispute according to the degrees of the courts in the appeals and cassation stages, which is what happens frequently in litigation before the courts.

The final provisions of arbitration ruling is not affected what some laws stipulate ,that they may be challenged with nullity for reasons mentioned in those laws, including the Egyptian Arbitration Law previously referred to, which states in Article (53) that *“The case for the nullity of the arbitration award is not accepted except in the following cases, if the arbitration award excludes the application of the law that the parties have agreed to apply to the subject of the dispute, and also if the arbitration tribunal is formed, or the arbitrators are appointed in a manner contrary to the law”*. Which usually relate to the authority and jurisdiction of the tribunal and the basic guarantees of litigation and public order in the country of the seat of arbitration, or the country in which the arbitration award is to be executed, and then they are a necessity for any judgment that terminates the litigation and which no arbitration ruling considered without.

This is confirmed with what the Cairo Court of Appeal ruled in its judgment that the case for the nullification of the arbitration ruling is not a challenge to appeal, and does not expand to reconsider the subject matter of the dispute, and that the judge of the case for the nullification does not have to review the arbitration ruling to assess its suitability, or monitor the arbitrators' good judgment, or the correctness of their diligence in understanding and adapting reality, or interpreting and applying the law, or the validity or contradiction of its causes, for that falls within the jurisdiction of the appellate judge, not the judge of nullification, and there is no dispute that the nullity lawsuit was a challenge for the appeal.

The experience of the banking arbitrator in the settling of Islamic banking disputes:

Islamic banking disputes arise as a result of implementing a banking process of an Islamic nature, or the application of Islamic banking norms, accordingly they always need arbitrators with a high degree of experience and advanced technical expertise in addition to that of the legal and jurisprudential side.

Islamic banking operations are characterized by being highly specialized, technical, and complex operations, combined with their legal and jurisprudential nature that are not properly regulated in law, as previously indicated, and then the nature of these technicalities and legal disputes makes it difficult to be resolved them through the courts, while specialists easily and straightforwardly resolve them. As an example, if one of the disputes arising from Islamic banking operations is brought before the ordinary court judge, that court will order that that the case be referred to an expert(s) to give their technical opinion about it, because these operations requires special scientific, technical and Sharia qualifications, as they are related to very complex financial and legal issues. Which may not be accepted by the conflicting parties; thus, foreign investor, and even the national investor working in financial and banking transactions, may dread resorting to the judiciary, fearing that national judges will not have the sufficient experience in the legal and jurisprudential issues to settle the disputes arising from this type of banking operations.

For judges, regardless of their experience in Islamic banking matters, are not comparable to banking arbitrators who specialize in Islamic financial and banking transactions, and who have the necessary

expertise to resolve disputes that are related to Islamic banking. And often enough, the use of experts who specialize in the field of conflict may lead to a protracted dispute. Thus, arbitration allows for the freedom to choose by the parties, arbitrators with high technical experience in Islamic banking and financial operations with further legal and jurisprudential understanding with this type of transaction.

It is worth noting that an arbitrator in Islamic banking transactions is not necessarily a legal person, but rather a technical one, preferably a banker, an expert, or a follower of the Islamic banking activities. Technically, the arbitrator is often a person skilled in the subject of the dispute or has a background in it, and this means that this person is fully aware of the appropriate norms in this field additional to possessing a certain skillset that judges of different countries do not hold, which is the ability to settle disputes easily by devising solutions that are inspired by reality, norms, habits, and principles abounds in international commercial life.

Therefore, it is not uncommon for the banking arbitration tribunal to be composed of one or more arbitrators who are experienced and specialized in Islamic financial and banking issues. The availability of that experience in the arbitrators will enable them to settle the Islamic banking dispute, in accordance with the correct legal, financial, and banking Islamic and Sharia principles. And in the same context, the Washington CD Convention of 1965 required arbitrators to have a requirement of experience, which was stipulated in Article (14) that “*Persons appointed to serve in the Commission shall have a great degree of morals and be recognized for their competence in the field of law, trade, industry and money, so that they can be relied upon in the practice of Judgment on matters is an independent judgment*”.

The application of Islamic law and rules most favorable to the conflict:

The law that the arbitration tribunals apply is always subjected to the will of individuals, whether that is before the dispute arose or after its emergence, and then parties involved can choose a foreign law different from the nationalities of the two parties, or for one of them, whilst the state courts does not have that privilege, for example, we do not find International trade and international investments exists in the best conditions for their growth and prosperity, unless they could break free from the restrictions of internal laws, which were originally established for simple transactions and seem incapable of keeping pace with modern international trade rules, which may lead to the judiciary’s inability to settle these disputes, if they relate to a rule of international trade rules as a result of its commitment to apply domestic laws.

Accordingly, arbitration is considered the tool to remedy this deficiency, so it would be more appropriate to assign the settlement of any dispute related to the rules of international trade to an arbitrator who is familiar with these laws and is familiar with them, thus facilitating the arbitration procedures, and it -arbitration- is not a guardian of the law of a country, so once it is agreed upon to resort to arbitration in a dispute, this agreement expresses the parties’ desire to subject their disputes to the law most appropriate to the dispute, even if this law had spawn from and arose automatically within the Islamic banking and financial sphere.

Therefore, we find that the regulation of the Mediation and Arbitration Center at the Union of Arab Banks states in paragraph (7) of Article (19) that “*the arbitral tribunal shall, and in all cases, take into account the provisions of the contract and the banking and commercial norms*”, and it is clear to us from this text that it is not a requirement to apply national banking customs and norms, but rather gave the arbitration board the freedom to apply the provisions of the contract, whether foreign or national.

3-Conclusion

It has been evident that the role of arbitration is growing in settling commercial disputes. Therefore, it is better for the parties involved in Islamic banking disputes to resort to an arbitration panel consisting of specialized people who have the experience and sufficient qualifications to settle the disputes, especially if the said disputes are related to credit, international banking operations, or newly and novel developed Islamic banking operations, to ensure disputes settlement through specialized arbitrators from the banking sector, with direct experience and expertise.

4-Reconditions

1. Codifying the provisions of Islamic law related to Islamic banking and financial operations and their new institutions, tools and contracts, by placing them in the form of legal articles that facilitate the adjudication of causes related to them in order to achieve the renewed legitimate interest and meet the changing needs of institutions and individuals.
2. The need to issue regulations and legislations to organize the arbitration for resolving disputes related to Islamic banking operations.
3. The necessity of stipulating the application of arbitration to every dispute with the operations that take place in accordance with the provisions of Islamic Sharia, and the parties must agree to refer it to arbitration in accordance with the provisions of the system, and this arbitration includes all Islamic banking operations and transactions, such as solidarity and leasing, which are carried out in accordance with Islamic law. This condition leads to the fact that the arbitral tribunal must consist of members who have knowledge and experience with the provisions of Islamic law, which may not be available in the regular courts that may consider the disputes, and which have been chosen under the public order.
4. The members of the panel must be chosen with experience and knowledge of the Sharia provisions related to Islamic banking transactions and operations, and this choice is to be made by the parties of the dispute, or the arbitration center, and we believe that the issue of good selection of members of the arbitration panel will support the Islamic operations and work to develop them, as all parties involved will have confidence in the smooth functioning banking operations, as well as with the good and speedy settlement of any disputes that may arise, for any reason.
5. The reference to the application of the provisions of the UNCITRAL system in the absence of a text in the center's system is considered a link to arbitration of disputes related to Islamic banking operations with the experience of international arbitration that took place through the UNCITRAL system. This is a very important outcome, as it will link Islamic banking transactions with international experiences, and then work to push Islamic operations to the new horizons, opening the way for the Islamic experience to be combined with international expertise and experiences.

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Author Information

Dr. Ahmed Moustafa AL-Dabousi El-Sayed

Assistant Professor in Commercial and Marine Law
College of Law – The American University in
Emirates
